

The evaluation of face-to-face learning is limited to the Indonesian language learning outcomes of class VII MTS Nur Al Zahrah DepokMuhammad Syauqi Ghozi¹, Irham Ramdani², Yayan Sudrajat³¹²³) Indraprasta PGRI UniversityCorrespondence Email : muhammadghozi2030@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine the results of the evaluation of seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah in learning Indonesian using CIPP. The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative. The results of this study indicate that the evaluation of the context of students' Indonesian learning outcomes in face-to-face learning is limited to the good category and is considered to have fulfilled all the stipulated provisions and regulations. Regarding the input in this study, it is included in the fairly good category, because the use of teacher learning resources only relies on books. The process in this research, learning Indonesian is going well. In product evaluation, student learning outcomes were reviewed based on report cards with an average of 82.6 in the cognitive domain, 81.3 in the psychomotor domain and in the affective domain as a whole quite good. Based on the results of the study, the authors conclude that it can be concluded that the limited face-to-face learning program at MTs Nur Al Zahrah during this pandemic is appropriate to continue with the procedures and rules that have been set because the learning outcomes of Indonesian class VII students are still in the good category.

Keywords: Evaluation, Learning Outcomes, Limited Face-to-face Learning**INTRODUCTION**

At the beginning of the pandemic, the government applied the principle of prioritizing health and safety in the provision of education by paying attention to the growth and development of Student and Student's rights during the pandemic. The face-to-face learning policy is implemented in stages to improve the quality of learning so that the results obtained are maximal and measurable. Through the Circular of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 4 of 2020, there is a change in the teaching and learning process, namely the implementation of learning from home, the abolition of national exams, the application of PPDB online, and the prohibition of crowding in the school environment. However, on December 7, 2020, the green and yellow zones can conduct face-to-face learning as needed, while the other two zones are still learning from home.

Online learning it turns out to have a negative impact and is not good for students. Student lose their passion for learning, discipline, and even responsibility. Parents do their schoolwork, making it difficult to measure learning outcomes. Therefore, the government decided to hold a limited face-to-face meeting (PTMT). Based on the Circular of the Minister of Education and Culture, the Depok City Government issued Circular Letter (SE) Number 443/645-Huk/Satgas regarding the implementation of the Health Protocol (Prokes) for Limited Face-to-Face Learning for Students. The SE states that PTMT can be implemented with a capacity of 50 percent. This circular letter was issued on Wednesday, November 10, 2021 based on the Instruction of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 57 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of Restrictions on Community Activities Level 3, Level 2, and Level 1 Corona Virus Disease 2019 in the Java and Bali Regions. The Depok City Government requires students to wear two-layer masks, namely medical masks and cloth masks, as well as see-through masks for students with hearing disabilities. Students and school residents must be in good health and not do activities that can cause crowds.

With the permission for schools to conduct face-to-face learning, MTs Nur Al Zahrah developed a curriculum based on a government circular. Face-to-face learning is held only for one class a day with a

duration of 40 minutes for each subject, while other classes that do not get a face-to-face schedule on that day, do virtual learning through the zoom meeting. All students whose classes get a face-to-face schedule are allowed to enter by complying with the health protocols that have been set, unless they are unable to get sick. With the duration of face-to-face learning which is only 40 minutes, the teacher is not enough to present the material in detail and evaluate students' understanding of the material presented. Teachers are dominantly active compared to students when the teaching and learning process takes place, so that the interaction between teachers and students in the learning process is still minimal.

(Masdafni, 2021) in his research on improving the mathematics learning outcomes of grade IX-C students of SMPN 1 Seberida in limited face-to-face learning explained, "students per class are divided into two study groups, namely group A and group B. Schedules are arranged for subjects only once. face-to-face meeting with a duration of 30 minutes. With a duration of 30 minutes, it is not enough for the teacher to present the material and test students' understanding of the material presented, thus the teacher resumes it when students are not in school with online learning through WAG or Google Classroom according to the schedule prepared by the school ". From the explanation of previous research,

There are differences in research objectives, research objects, limited face-to-face learning regulations, and students' problems with learning, with research compiled by the author.

Based on the description above, the formulation of the problem to be studied is how the results of the evaluation of student learning in class VII MTs Nur Al Zahrah in learning Indonesian using CIPP. With the aim of the study to find the results of the evaluation of the VII grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah in learning Indonesian using CIPP.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted on May 17 to June 14 2022, the data source was taken from class VII students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok for the academic year 2021/2022 totaling 15 students. The approach used by the author in this research is descriptive qualitative. The data collected in the form of descriptions of context, input, process, and product in the form of descriptions and descriptions of the results of the limited face-to-face learning evaluation of Indonesian students at MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok. The focus in this study is the evaluation of limited face-to-face learning outcomes at MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok with a subfocus on Indonesian language learning outcomes for seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah in terms of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains.

The instruments used are observation, interviews, and document analysis. Observations were carried out carefully to observe the implementation of limited face-to-face learning. In line with that, interviews were conducted individually to find out the response of each student to limited PTM by recording each point from the answers obtained and recording answers using a cellphone audio recorder as backup data, and document analysis conducted through student learning outcomes assessment data. during the implementation of the limited PTM owned by the seventh grade Indonesian teacher at MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok.

RESULTS

The evaluation of face-to-face learning is limited to the Indonesian language learning outcomes for seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok. An analysis and discussion was carried out through four stages, namely context, input, process, and product. The results found through evaluation using the CIPP model are as follows:

Table 1
Findings of Data Aspects of Evaluation Context, Input, Process, Product

Aspect	Found	Data Source	Category
Context	The application of face-to-face learning is limited	School Documentation	.Good
	Arrangement of study group sessions	School Documentation	Very good
	Objectives of developing Indonesian language learning for grade VII students	School Documentation.	Good
Result		Good	
Input	basis Legal learning Indonesian	Language Teacher Documentation	Good

	Plan implementation learning Indonesian	Language Teacher Documentation	Good
	Resources Learning Language Indonesian	Student Interview & Observation	Fairly
	Result		Good
Process	Instructional Objectives	Observation	Good
	Instructional materials	Observation	Good
	Teaching and Learning Activities	Observation	Good
	Result		Good
Product	Cognitif	Documentation	Good
	Psychomotor	Documentation	Good
	Afektif	Documentation	Good
	Result		Good

The author obtained data on Indonesian language learning outcomes for seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok based on documentation in the form of report cards obtained through their homeroom teachers in the form of copies of the overall results of subject scores. The data obtained were then analyzed by the author to obtain the results of learning Indonesian as a whole.

Evaluation Context

Limited face-to-face learning is motivated by government decisions in learning during the transition period of the corona virus pandemic. Based on the Circular of the Minister of Education and Culture, the Depok City Government issued Circular Letter (SE) No. 443/645- Huk/Satgas related to the implementation of the Health Protocol (Prokes) Limited Face-to-Face Learning for Students. The SE states that PTMT can be implemented with a capacity of 50 percent. Based on the table, the first point is the application of a face-to-face learning time limitation which is only 40 minutes as a benchmark for student learning outcomes and is categorized as "good" because it does not significantly affect student learning outcomes. This was conveyed by one of the seventh grade students named Syaena during the interview, as follows: "Limited face-to-face learning does not affect my learning outcomes. The effect of face-to-face learning is limited depending on the student, if he understands the material seriously, it is certain can get the desired result."

The same thing was also explained by him in the interview process conducted in class: "I understand the lessons in this limited face-to-face learning better than distance learning/PJJ. Because online learning makes me dizzy."

Based on these findings, it can be explained that the application of a face-to-face learning time limit is something that must be applied by every educational institution at this time. MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok has properly imposed a face-to-face learning time limit from Monday, August 23, 2021. Face-to-face learning limited advance has the aim of regenerating the learning spirit / learning mentality of MTs Nur Al Zahrah students who are felt to have started to decline during distance learning activities or PJJ the second point related to the arrangement of study group sessions, the school prepares and circulates policies related to the schedule of student study sessions through a circular letter of limited face-to-face learning. But over time, in terms of the receding spread of the corona virus, MTs Nur Al Zahrah carried out limited face-to-face learning 100%. In a sense, learning was carried out simultaneously by the entire school community with time limit note. Based on these findings, it can be explained that the preparation of study group sessions at MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok is considered "very good". This is evidenced by the progress related to the development of limited face-to-face learning which over time is carried out simultaneously. Based on this progress, it can facilitate the acquisition of Indonesian language learning development goals in the form of students' ability to speak Indonesian properly and correctly and to be able to appreciate Indonesian language and literature according to the situation and level of learning experience.

It can be concluded that the people of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok have complied with all the rules and regulations that have been set, such as obeying health protocols, arriving on time, and using uniform standards. Schedule of study group sessions at MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok during limited face-to-face learning obtained through analysis of documents owned by the school.

Evaluation Input

The limited face-to-face learning evaluation of the Indonesian language learning outcomes of seventh grade students at MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok is described based on the findings, in the first point it can be explained that the legal basis for learning Indonesian has been reviewed from the Graduate Competency Standards (SKL) and has been implemented with "good". This is evidenced by the author through document analysis conducted based on the values of knowledge, skills, and attitudes of students through

the documentation of the VII grade Indonesian language teacher.

In the next aspect contained in the second point, regarding the annual program of Indonesian language learning, it can be explained that in general the limited face-to-face learning at MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok has been able to arrange a program of activities that are the main goals of student learning success. In line with the planning and implementation of learning activities during the transition period of the corona virus pandemic organized by the school for one year, administratively there has been an increase, especially in the preparation of learning planning programs. Learning Implementation Plan (RPP) revised.

In the next aspect contained in the third point, regarding Indonesian language learning resources, it can be explained that Indonesian language learning that takes place in the classroom is more dominant using books. This can be proven through the results of an interview with one of the seventh grade students named Syaena regarding the use of Indonesian language teacher learning resources, as follows: "Teachers often use the "Experienced Indonesian Language" textbook in guiding us to study in class."

Book learning resources are the most important teaching material, but it would be better if the teacher was able to expand their learning resources so that students' interest in learning could be increased. Broadly speaking, the use of teaching materials for the VII grade Indonesian language teacher at MTs Nur Al Zahrah can be categorized as "sufficient" because it is in accordance with the guidelines for using the applicable learning design teaching materials.

Evaluation The Process

Evaluation process of the face-to-face learning Based on the results of observations, it can be explained that Indonesian language learning activities are as follows:

a. Instructional Objectives

- 1) The author explains all specific instructional objectives to students, so that they know what they are trying to achieve.
- 2) Specific instructional objectives that are realized in learning activities can be said to be good.

b. Instructional Materials

- 1) The teacher explains orally the lesson material, occasionally he looks at the source book to test the truth of the material he teaches.
- 2) Mastering the material to be taught to students.

c. Teaching and Learning Activities

- 1) The teaching method used is lecture and question and answer or two teaching methods alternately.
- 2) Student learning activities, only listen / pay attention to the teacher's description.
- 3) The teacher does not use teaching aids except writing on the blackboard.
- 4) Teachers provide more information orally.
- 5) The teacher asks students to write down the results of the lessons that have been discussed at that time.

Evaluation The Product

Evaluation products of face-to-face learning This can be seen from the values obtained by students while participating in Indonesian language learning during face-to-face meetings are limited, both from the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. The values obtained by means of document analysis in the form of a copy of the grade VII report card owned by the Indonesian teacher.

Cognitive domain can be categorized as "good". This is reviewed based on table 2 of the results of the Indonesian language report cards for class VII students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok, the majority of which are in the "B" predicate. Of the 15 students, the knowledge value of grade VII students who were in the "C" predicate was only three students, namely Ikram, Al Farizi, and Hafiz, while the other 13 students were in the "B" predicate.

The affective domain of students in learning Indonesian for class VII students can be categorized as "good". This is seen from the results of the values of social and spiritual attitudes on Indonesian language report cards for all seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok which are in the "good" predicate. The affective domain of student learning outcomes that are in the "good" predicate can be described as follows;

Social

Attitude Good attitude in appreciating the nobility of Pancasila values as the nation's view of life by always paying attention to the rules of madrasah, having good honesty, having good discipline, having good responsibility, having good tolerance, having a good mutual cooperation attitude, having good manners and having a good attitude. good confidence.

Spiritual Attitude Spiritual

Attitude that is shown both in appreciating the behavior of faith and piety to God Almighty and having noble character in life in madrasas and society, diligent in praying, diligent in greeting, very diligent in participating in congregational prayers and good at being grateful.

The psychomotor domain of students in learning Indonesian class VII can be categorized as "good". This is seen from the results of the Indonesian language report cards for all seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok which are in the "good" predicate. Of the 15 students, the grade VII students' skill scores were at the "C" predicate, 6 students, namely Anjaba, Fachri, Haikal, Al Farizi, Hafiz, and Ikram.

DISCUSSION

Limited face-to-face learning at MTs Nur Al Zahrah has 100 percent been carried out face-to-face, it's just that the learning hours are limited. The duration of each subject only lasts for 40 minutes per meeting, including Indonesian subjects. If it is calculated within a week, teaching and learning activities for Indonesian class VII subjects only have 80 minutes. Indonesian class VII subjects really need time that is relevant to the learning material that dominates reading activities to identify important points in each material, thus requiring teachers to be more dominantly active in classroom learning than students.

Referring to the results of the study, it can be explained that in the aspect of evaluating the context of limited face-to-face learning on Indonesian language learning outcomes for class VII students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok, it has been based on the needs that need to be met, namely in the context of the importance of student learning outcomes through limited face-to-face learning. . This is shown through the three aspects which include; (1) the implementation of face-to-face learning time restrictions, (2) the preparation of study group sessions, and (3) the objectives of developing Indonesian language learning for class VII students. From these points, in general, the elements of context in student learning outcomes have been met through limited face-to-face learning. This shows that the context has been carried out in accordance with the objectives of the learning. The stage of the context in this study seeks to see student learning outcomes in terms of readiness in planning the implementation of limited face-to-face learning by MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok. The results of this study are in line with the research results of Masnur, et al. related to preparation in planning the implementation of limited face-to-face learning by the school is included in the "Good" category. The analysis on the context has provided an illustration that the evaluation carried out on the Indonesian language learning outcomes of class VII students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok in a limited face-to-face learning program has been carried out well. Referring to this, MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok has properly imposed time limits and the division of learning sessions in face-to-face learning with the aim of regenerating the learning spirit / learning mentality of MTs Nur Al Zahrah students who are felt to be starting to decline during distance learning activities or PJJ.

Discussion on evaluation of Indonesian language learning outcomes for seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok in a limited face-to-face learning program, in the second stage is input.aspect stages input in this study indicate that the competence of supporting learning outcomes for class VII students at MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok is "good". The legal basis and plans for implementing Indonesian language learning have been implemented "well", but the learning resources are still in the "enough" category, it would be better if the teacher could reflect on learning by expanding their learning resources such as empowering print and online, so that students' interest in learning can be further improved.

Evaluation of the process in the discussion of the evaluation of Indonesian language learning outcomes for seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok in a limited face-to-face learning program, seeks to see the learning process in class.evaluation process, it can be explained that the findings in this study indicate that the learning activities in the classroom that have been carried out by teachers and grade VII students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah in Indonesian subjects have been running "well". This is indicated by the types of activities that have been carried out well and smoothly based on the results of research ranging from instructional objectives, mastery of lesson materials, to teaching and learning activities in the classroom. This shows that the implementation of classroom learning activities that have been carried out

by teachers and students of class VII MTs Nur Al Zahrah in Indonesian subjects have really been carried out well.

Evaluation of the product in the discussion of the evaluation of Indonesian language learning outcomes for seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok in a limited face-to-face learning program. In the results of this evaluation, based on the results of the study, it shows that in general Indonesian language learning has been able to produce products "good" evaluation product include Indonesian language learning outcomes in terms of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains which have a "good" category. Regarding 6 students whose learning outcomes are still at a sufficient level in the psychomotor aspect, namely, Anjaba with a score of 78, Fachri with a value of 79, Haikal with a value of 79, Al Farizi with a value of 77, Hafiz with a value of 79, and Ikram with a value of 76, while in the cognitive aspect, there are 3 students whose learning outcomes are still at a sufficient level in the psychomotor aspect, namely, Ikram with a value of 76, Al Farizi with a value of 78, and Hafiz with a value of 79 which is a percentage of the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) predicate above, the results of learning Indonesian for class VII students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah are generally considered "good". This is also shown in the learning achievement of grade VII students who are projected to pass the Scientific Writing Selection Competition (KLTI) in abstract form organized by the Youth Scientific Group (KIR) MAN 1 Kediri, the results of which are attached on the appendix page. In line with the success of student learning in learning Indonesian, it is shown in the performance agenda in the presentation model in class which is done well and according to the direction of the Indonesian teacher. The following is a picture of the results of observations in the form of presentation performance in Indonesian for class VII students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the evaluation using the CIPP model on limited face-to-face learning research data on Indonesian language learning outcomes for seventh grade students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok, it can be concluded that the context has been implemented based on the needs that need to be met to review learning outcomes. students in face-to-face learning during the pandemic, namely the limitation of face-to-face learning time and the preparation of study group sessions. This shows that the context has been carried out well and in accordance with the objectives of learning Indonesian. The next aspect is input, the results of the study state that in this aspect there are still findings that need to be improved regarding Indonesian language learning resources such as using print and online, so that students' interest and enthusiasm for learning can be increased. But overall, the evaluation results on the input are quite good. This can be seen from the legal basis in the form of graduate competency standards and work programs that are sufficient in learning Indonesian. evaluation Process, research results state that this aspect has been implemented well.

This can be seen from the data obtained by the author on the mastery of teaching materials, instructional objectives, and well realized Indonesian language learning activities. evaluation Product, research results state that this aspect has been implemented well. Overall student learning outcomes in the field of Indonesian language studies which are reviewed based on the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains of class VII students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah Depok are included in the good category. This can be seen through student learning outcomes in the form of report cards with an average result of 82.6 in the cognitive domain, while the average result in the psychomotor domain is 81.3 and in the affective domain as a whole is fairly good. This is because teachers are professional teachers and students who are able to understand learning comprehensively.

In order to face the obstacles in the learning outcomes of class VII students of MTs Nur Al Zahrah in learning Indonesian during the PTM period, the things that need to be done are limited, namely teachers in the field of Indonesian language studies should be able to expand teaching materials such as using print and online, so that students can be more enthusiastic in learning. It is recommended that schools and Indonesian language teachers be able to be more active in providing direction, supervision, and guidance to students in limited face-to-face learning, and students to increase their enthusiasm for learning, especially in learning Indonesian and keep listening to teacher directions in the implementation of limited face-to-face learning, considering the condition that has not fully recovered from exposure to the corona virus pandemic.

REFERENCES

- Minanurokhim, MA, Haq, NYI, & Basit, A. (2021). Limited Face-to-face Learning Safe Guide. Compiler, T., Field, T., Directorate, P., Elementary, S., Education, K., Technology, D., & Elementary School, D. (2021). Limited Face-to-face Learning Guidelines. 1–10.
- H Kara, OAMA (2014). Active Learning During a Pandemic. In Paper Knowledge . Toward a Media History of Documents (Vol. 7, Issue 2).
- Supriyadi. (2013). Evaluation of Indonesian Language Learning. In UNG Press Gorontalo.
- Tanuwijaya, NS, & Tambunan, W. (2021). Alternative Learning Model Solutions to Overcome the Risk of Declining Learning Outcomes in Limited Face-to-face Learning in the Covid-19 Pandemic Period (Case Study of Education Policy Analysis). *Journal of Educational Management*, 10(02), 80–90.
- Becker, FG (2015). *Learning Evaluation*. Bandung: Faithful Library.
- Ropii, M., & Fahrurrozi, M. (2019). *Evaluation of Learning Outcomes*. Yogyakarta: Student Library.
- Asrul, et al. (2014). *Learning Evaluation*. Bandung: Media Library Masnur, Aminullah, Haliq, muh Idham, Elihami, & Rahmat. (2021). Evaluasi Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran Tatap Muka (PTM) pada Satuan Pendidikan Sekolah Dasar Terbatas Dikabupaten Enrekang. *Pendidikan*, 5(2), 1020–1026.
- Purwanto, N. (2013). *Prinsip – Prinsip Evaluasi Pengajaran*. Bandung : PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Supriatna, U. (2021). Flipped Classroom: Metode Pembelajaran Tatap Muka Terbatas pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Ideas: Jurnal Pendidikan, Sosial, Dan Budaya*, 7(3), 57. <https://doi.org/10.32884/ideas.v7i3.408>
- Tarigan, RMRB (2019). Pengaruh Sarana Dan Prasarana Sekolah Terhadap Prestasi Belajar Siswa Kelas V Sd Negeri Kec. Tiga Binanga Tahun Ajaran 2018/2019. *Universitas Quality*, 4(80), 4.